

SHORT AND LONG RANGE ORDERED SURFACE STRUCTURES OF SEGREGATED SPECIES ON Fe(100)

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Abstract

The local structure of segregated nonmagnetic species on Fe(100) has been studied with LEED, Auger and STM spectroscopy. Distinct surface arrangements as well as ordered structures are observed for carbon and phosphor segregations as a function of the preparation conditions (annealing and sputtering) and of the structural quality of Fe(100) single crystals. The comparison between spectroscopic features and atomically resolved STM images reveals the presence of carbon self-assembled stripes with a regular pattern on nanometer lateral scale.

Keywords: Thin films, Surface Magnetism, Nanostructured Materials.*

1.Introduction

Many material properties are decisively controlled by the structure and the composition of the surface, when changes occur due to adsorption and/or segregation processes [1]. The control of such processes is of fundamental importance for both technological and fundamental aspects of surface science. In this paper, we report a detailed study of the Fe(100) surface segregation: from the combined analysis of: LEED, Auger and STM data we are able to observe and disentangle the presence of metastable phases of segregated species, some of them displaying one or more characteristic self-assembled as well as periodic arrangement.

2.Experiment

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Experiments were performed at the sample preparation facility of the APE-INFM (Advanced Photoemission Experiment) at ELETTRA [2], in a base vacuum of 4×10^{-11} mbar for both LEED-AUGER and STM chambers. Room temperature STM images were obtained by transferring the sample under vacuum. Sputtering (Ar^+ bombardment, 800 eV) and annealing procedures were used to obtain segregation. As a function of the annealing temperature as well as of the annealing time the different segregations were found reproducibly in different temperature regions: Carbon from about 500 K, and phosphor from about 850 K. A metastable surface is established where the segregated species form an adlayer structure with local coordination and with, or without, long range symmetry. The thermal promotion of a new segregating specie modifies the surface by further superposing a new structure, or by atomic substitution.

3.Results and Discussion

Segregation of Fe(100) surface is well known as a substitutional process: as annealing temperature grows, respectively carbon, silicon and sulphur coverages reach equilibrium and are subsequently 'kicked out' by the next impurity element [3]. Auger spectra are presented in fig.1, for different segregation temperatures. The ratio between Fe LMM Auger lines and impurity signal allows to estimate the coverage. LEED picture of fig.2(a) reveals the presence of a 'classical' $c(2 \times 2)$ reconstruction at low segregation temperature (573 K) of carbon. Due to the misalignment of the Fe(100) surface, we found a $c(3\sqrt{2} \times \sqrt{2})$ reconstruction at the carbon segregation temperature from about 650 K to 850 K (fig.2(b)). This structure is mostly due to the presence of 100 Angstrom wide terraces on the Fe(100) single crystal, corresponding to an uncertainty of 1 degree in the crystal planes. This probably promotes the carbon segregation in an ordered arrangement, as shown in fig.3 over a 825×825 Angstrom STM image. Moreover, the Auger carbon spectra (fig.1) display the characteristic up-down line shape that is reminiscent of transition metal carbides (namely, 'carbide' carbon) [4,5], corresponding to the signature of the iron-carbon bonding at the interface layer.

The $c(3\sqrt{2} \times \sqrt{2})$ reconstruction is confirmed by STM images of the carbon segregated surface in fig.4. A local zig-zag chain structure aligned with the $\langle 11 \rangle$ direction is found. A further confirmation of the $c(3\sqrt{2} \times \sqrt{2})$ reconstruction has been obtained by Fourier Filtering of the STM images, well reproducing the LEED patterns of fig.2(b). The zig-zag chain does not exceed more than about 20 Angstrom and either breaks or changes preferential direction by 90 degrees. The distance between the nearest neighbor atoms is about 2.9 Angstrom and it is equal to the lattice constant of bcc iron, that is, the distance between two iron atoms in (100) surface, and is quite bigger than the distance of two carbon atoms which are bonded with covalent bonding (1.2-1.5 Angstrom). The white region observed in STM images at the break point of the zig-zag line, however, indicates the existence of the dangling bond, that is, carbon atoms bond nearest two carbon atoms except the break point. And the angle between two bonding directions is always 90degrees. This directional bonding suggests the C-C bonding is covalent bonding in spite of the large nearest neighbor distance (2.9 Angstrom).

At higher temperatures (about 850 K), phosphor segregation occurs, as revealed from the inspection of Auger signals. The STM images of fig.5 shows two stage of the phosphor segregation: at an early stage (fig.5(a)), phosphor atoms prefer to stick to the corner of the carbon chains, where an unsaturated bond is probably available. The distance between two nearest phosphor atoms is about 4.1 Angstrom and it shows the phosphor atoms form $c(2 \times 2)$ reconstruction. When the segregation process has reached the saturation level, almost all the terraces are covered by the phosphor atoms chains (fig.5(b)). Contrary to carbon behaviour, the phosphor atoms prefer to form long chains with non-periodic arrangement, and no long range order.

4.Conclusion

In conclusion, We have studied by STM, LEED and Auger the atomic structure of segregated carbon and phosphor from Fe(100) single crystal. Fe(3%Si) single crystal exposing the (100) surface does segregate various impurities when annealed in the temperature range 600-950 K. Carbon lines , based on

$c(3\sqrt{2} \times \sqrt{2})$ surface reconstruction, are found in zig-zag arrangement. At higher annealing temperature, phosphor atoms bind first to the corners of the carbon zig-zag chains and form a two dimensional structure. At higher density of segregated phosphor winding chains, with no long range order are observed.

Acknowledgements

G.P. thanks P.Torelli and F. Sirotti for valuable suggestions as well as for the use of their samples.

Authors wish to express their thanks to D. Krizmancic for the software support. This work was partially supported by EC, under contract n. HPRI-2001-50062.

5.References

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List of Graphics Captions

Fig.1: Auger Spectra at different annealing temperatures. Phosphor appears at above 850 K.

Fig.2: LEED image at different annealing temperatures. (a) After a low temperature annealing, 'classical' broad $c(2 \times 2)$ is seen (573 K). (b) A $c(3\sqrt{2} \times \sqrt{2})$ reconstruction is found after middle temperature annealing (823 K). (c) After a high temperature annealing at 948 K.

Fig.3: 825x825 angstrom STM image. $V_s = +200$ mV, $I = 0.2$ nA

Fig.4: STM image after carbon segregation at 823K. (a) 165x165 angstrom. $V_s = +400$ mV, $I = 0.1$ nA. (b) 41x41 angstrom. $V_s = +200$ mV, $I = 0.2$ nA.

Fig.5: STM image after phosphor segregation at 948K. (a) Low coverage region. 82x82 angstrom. $V_s = +100$ mV, $I = 0.25$ nA. (b) High coverage region. 165x165 angstrom. $V_s = +400$ mV, $I = 0.5$ nA.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

Fig. 5

